

USING AUDIO-LINGUAL METHOD ON TEACHING INTERMEDIATE LEVEL STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7440544>

Abstract: Listening is one of the four basic skills in learning a foreign language besides listening, reading, and writing. It has been taught since the students entered a junior high school, however, there are some difficulties faced by vocational school students to listen to the recording. The alternative method is Audio-lingual teaching method. The objectives of the study were to explain the students' ability to recognize word meaning in the context and to recognize the content of the text. The design of the research used a collaborative classroom action research (CAR). This kind of research was designed by a group which consisted of teacher and researcher from the educational university. The place of this research was in SMK YAPIP MAKASSAR. The samples in this research were the students at the second year of class 2 Akuntansi 1. After conducting the research, the students' means score showed the improvement in cycle 2. It is concluded that using audio-lingual could help to improve students' listening comprehension.

Key words: listening comprehension, audio-lingual, recognizing word meaning and the content of the text, classroom action research

To understand what an audio-lingual language learning method is, it is suggested referring to a dictionary entry. The dictionary of methodological terms says that the audio-lingual teaching method is a method of teaching a foreign language, which provides for the use of the auditory channel of perception in the course of classes and repeated listening and reproduction of strictly selected structures, sample sentences after the speaker, which leads to their automation. Based on Skinner's Behaviorism theory, it assumed that a human being can be trained using a system of reinforcement.

Correct behaviour receives positive feedback, while errors receive negative feedback. This approach to learning is similar to the Direct Method, in that the lesson takes place entirely in the target language. Emphasis is on the acquisition of patterns in common everyday dialogue. The Audio-lingual Method was widely used in the 1950s and 1960s, and the emphasis was not on the understanding of words, but rather on the acquisition of structures and patterns in common everyday dialogue. In 2000 scientists Larsen and Freeman mentioned that,"

Audio-lingual method, like the direct method, is also an oral approach. However, it is very different in that rather than emphasizing vocabulary acquisition through exposure to its use in situations, the Audio-lingual method drills students in the use of grammatical sentence patterns."

Also, they added that it was thought that the way to acquire the sentence patterns of the target language was through conditioning helping learners to respond correctly to stimuli through shaping and reinforcement. Thus, the audio lingual method refers to the method that it is compressed on the chain drill to mastery the target language by memorizing and repeat, and the wrongness of speaking is avoided.

The audio-lingual approach

- The audio-lingual approach dominated foreign language teaching in the 1950s and 1960s.
- Its rise is partly due to the fact that because of the rapid increase of international trade, travel, and commerce, ever more people needed to learn English (the new lingua franca). That includes 'intellectually less gifted' people.
- The major aim is to enable all learners to use English in everyday oral communication. Speaking is put before and above writing.
- The claim is that by the imitation of good examples and the fast correction of errors everyone can learn a second language. There is no need for abstract rule knowledge. ("Englisch für alle", 1964).
- Pattern drills and the use of the language laboratory are typical of the teaching methods used under the audio-lingual approach.

The theoretical background to the audio-lingual approach

- Behaviouristic theories of learning, paired with a linguistic approach that takes an interest in the surface structures of language only, form the scientific background of the audio-lingual approach.
- The radical behaviourist position is that people are like animals and learn 'things' by trial-and-error and/or the imitation of what others say/do, not by a creative (cognitive) construction of phrases.
- Behaviourists claim that all learning rests on an association which is formed between a stimulus and a response (S-R theories). Famous experiments to prove that are Pavlov's experiments with dogs, and Thorndike's experiments with pigeons and rats in mazes.
- If learning rests on imitation then teachers must use English only in class. And their English must be good (correct) English.

Audio-lingual method

The audio-lingual method, Army Method, or New Key,[1] is a style of teaching used in teaching foreign languages. It is based on behaviorist theory, which professes that certain traits of living things, and in this case humans, could be trained through a system of reinforcement—correct use of a trait would receive positive feedback while incorrect use of that trait would receive negative feedback.

This approach to language learning was similar to another, earlier method called the direct method. Like the direct method, the audio-lingual method advised that students be taught a language directly, without using the students' native language to explain new words or grammar in the target language. However, unlike the direct method, the audio-lingual method didn't focus on teaching vocabulary. Rather, the teacher drilled students in the use of grammar.

Applied to language instruction, and often within the context of the language lab, this means that the instructor would present the correct model of a sentence and the students would have to repeat it. The teacher would then continue by presenting new words for the students to sample in the same structure. In audio-lingualism, there is no explicit grammar instruction—everything is simply memorized in form. The idea is for the students to practice the particular construct until they can use it spontaneously. In this manner, the lessons are built on static drills in which the students have little or no control on their own output; the teacher is expecting a particular response and not providing that will result in a student receiving negative feedback. This type of activity, for the foundation of language learning, is in direct opposition with communicative language teaching.

Charles Fries, the director of the English Language Institute at the University of Michigan, the first of its kind in the United States, believed that learning structure, or grammar was the starting point for the student. In other words, it was the students' job to orally recite the basic sentence patterns and grammatical structures. The students were only given “enough vocabulary to make such drills possible.” (Richards, J.C. et-al. 1986). Fries later included principles for behavioural psychology, as developed by B.F. Skinner, into this method.

Since, everything has pros and cons. In the following plus and minus sides of audio-lingual method will be clarified.

1. Availability. Indeed, this method of language learning is extremely accessible. Because, students or independent learners can just open the app store and will find language learning programs based on the audio-lingual method. The most

popular are DUOlinguo and Memrise. Some of them are paid, some are not. But even paid apps turn out to be much cheaper than a lesson with a teacher. Besides that, they are time-saving and don't require special time or tutorial classes.

3. Ease of use. Everything here is just straight up to disgrace. Learners have a set of words, pictures, cards and cubes-blocks that you listen to repeatedly and correlate with each other to get a phrase by clicking on them or dragging them. Nothing complicated.

4. Stability and consistency of the teaching method. Training always takes place according to the same scenario. First, students see a set of words, voice acting and pictures for them, usually no more than 2-3 words are given per lesson. Then they work out these words by choosing the translation, writing, pronouncing, constantly listening and repeating aloud. Each card is read out, so students hear one word or expression many, many times, so that they will not be able not to remember. Subsequently, complication occurs. New words are added and phrases are expanded. They become more detailed and complex. If you had the phrase "A girl drinks milk", then after a couple of lessons this phrase turns into "A little girl drinks milk in the kitchen."

5. Comfort and duration of the lesson. Actually, there is no need to talk about convenience. Learner can practice when it is convenient for them. Even if the desire to repeat the English pronouns overwhelmed his/her at midnight, it is possible to just download the app. In addition the length of your lesson should be controlled by the learner and it can be 5 minutes a day or 2 hours. It all depends only on their desire and time possibilities.

CONCLUSION: Thus, the audio-lingual method is a good addition when teaching English or another foreign language with a teacher, either individually or in a group. You can also recommend it to already experienced people who have learned one or two languages, if they understand the logic and structure of languages and are ready to take on the next one.

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